

THE ANSWER TO THE PROBLEMS OF LOGICAL NEGATION REQUIRES A CRITICAL REFINEMENT OF ARISTOTLE'S DEFINITION OF CONTRARY OPPOSITION.

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Summary. A modification to the Aristotelian definition of contrary opposites is proposed, accentuating the function of the adequate use of the principle of contradiction and the exclusive disjunction; which allows us to rethink, and even resolve, issues that have been under discussion for a long time, ranging from the validity of the classic Logical Square of Opposition, to the ad hoc of Russell's Theory of Descriptions, or the role of scalar terms in logical negation. For this purpose, it is taken as a common thread the critical analysis of the debates about the ambiguity, or not, of logical negation, its possible overlap between contradictory opposites and contraries in various propositions, and the scope of empty terms and category mistakes. And we detect various fallacies on the matter, resulting from an inadvertent change in the universe of discourse.

Keywords: Contradictory and contraries _ Meaning _ Empty terms _ Logical Square of Opposition _ Category errors _ Fallacies _ Universe of discourse _ Semantics _ Information _ Ambiguity _ Linguistics _ Theory of descriptions _ Scalar propositions _ Exclusive disjunction _ Abelard _ Frege _ Russell _ Jespersen _ Chomsky _ Horn _ Negation

Introduction.

In his analysis of the facts of logic, Aristotle defines the *contrary* statements as those that cannot be true together; but both can be false at the same time. We maintain here that, to achieve greater syntactic rigor in the delimitation of what contradiction and contrariety are (and therefore the logical negation), it is logically necessary to introduce the following *restriction*, which will be explained in the body of this writing: the contrary statements are those that cannot be true together, but both can be false at the same time *if and only if* two or more possible singularizations of meaning within a given universe of discourse correspond to any of them. If, otherwise, there is only one possible singularity, the contradictory is equal to the only contrary, and the most restrictive condition, the contradictory relationship, imposes the logical limit, whereby both propositions, the original and its negation, cannot be true or false at the same time.

The history of logic has witnessed various approaches to negation after Aristotle's view, such as the Stoic school in antiquity, or Abelard's work in the medieval period, and they are revisited by modern logicians like Boole, Frege, Russell, Quine, and others. These approaches raise issues, for

instance, about the soundness of the Logical Square of Opposition that was constructed based on the Aristotelian texts; or the debate about the ambiguity or clarity of negation; the distinction between the contrary and contradictory negations of a statement, the impact of empty terms or categorization errors on negation; or the function of terms that indicate scales, viz. different gradations in judgments.

In this paper, we argue, first, that the discussion on that topic has been obscured by a confusion between the *meaning* of ambiguous propositions and the meaning of the corresponding propositions that single them out, which are not mere reformulations of the former, but rather different statements. We claim that it is necessary and fruitful to distinguish clearly (which the authors mentioned do not do): the meaning of an ambiguous negation of a proposition X remains ambiguous even if it is elucidated, since the elucidations correspond to propositions different from X. Continuing our critical exposition, we show that, by applying strict logic to this gap, we can prevent confusion between the contradictory opposite and the contrary opposites of a statement (confusion that appears in the arguments and examples of several writers discussed here). Next, we propose the *modification*, grounded on the description of those syntactic facts, to the definition made from *Aristotle* of what is the contrary opposite of a proposition; and we explain the role that exclusive disjunctions have at these points. Also, we specify the method of assigning truth values to ambiguous utterances.

In the subsequent point, the discussion sheds light on some of the problems that we raised at the outset, such as identifying fallacies that involve the inadvertent shifting of the universe of discourse in arguments, or ad hoc formulations, as in Russell's Theory of Descriptions.

We aim to clarify the distinction between abstract and concrete propositions by examining critically various arguments and examples from different authors who have diverse views and nuances on this topic. We evaluate their validity by applying the strict differentiation between the meaning of ambiguous (or abstract) and singular (or concrete) propositions, as well as the logical principles of contradictory and contraries opposites, exclusive disjunction, and the scope of the universe of discourse.

An evaluation of the shortcomings of Abelard's criticism about the classical Square of Logical Opposition.

Following the principles of Aristotle's *Organon*, later logicians developed the diagram known as the *Logical Square of Opposition*. This format involves analyzing the relations between the quantity (all, some) and the quality (affirmative, negative) of propositions. For example, Apuleius explains how these relations determine the validity of inferences [2: V, p. 87], and Boethius provides a detailed description of the diagram that represents these relations graphically [5, pp. 70-78]. The diagram looks like this:

It is customary to call its instances:

A: Universal affirmative (All S are P).

E: Universal negative (No S is P).

I: Particular affirmative (Some S is P).

O: Particular negative (Not all S are P).

In this way, occurs the relationships of contradiction, which is the mere negation of a proposition (for example, All S are P versus Not all S are P), or contrariety, which goes beyond mere negation (All S are P vs. No S is P).

But there have been, at least since *Abelard*, in the 12th century AD, *objections* to such an approach. Analyzing propositions like

(1) Every man is just,

he states in his *Dialectic* [1: Introduction, pp. LVII-LVIII; and pp. 183-184] that if no man exists, that is, the *subject is empty*, neither the expression (1) nor its contradictory proposition

(2) Not every man is just.

are true (perhaps for a non-human intelligence), despite being contradictory according to the Aristotelian definition, concordant to which in such a case one must be true and the other false, and in no way both false or both true at the same time.

As Aristotle states, (1) would be false, and his mere negation, (2), which proscribes the existence of

a middle term, would be true. He says,

For take 'Socrates is sick' and 'Socrates is not sick': if he exists it is clear that one or the other of them will be true or false, and equally if he does not ; for if he does not exist 'he is sick' is false but 'he is not sick' true. Thus it would be distinctive of these alone-opposed affirmations and negations- that always one or the other of them is true or false. [3, Categories: 13^b 30-35].

Agree with this position, (1) is false because it predicates that every man is, i.e., exists, by affirming that there is a specific quality of such men (being just) that can only occur if the bearers of such quality exist (unless let's talk about impossible smiles without a cat, except as a literary device). When the assumption is that no man exists, is it true or false (2)? Syntactically, by the principle of contradiction, (2) must be true, because it is the negation of (1), which is false.

Another point that supports (2) true is that (2) is an ambiguous expression, that is, indeterminate (in this paper we will use the terms "*ambiguous*", "*indeterminate*" and "*abstract*" interchangeably for a meaningful statement but with a lack of specificity). In formal logic, it corresponds to a quantified predicate Fx that does not have a truth value by itself, but rather depends either syntactically on a previous truth value of its negation $\neg Fx$; or, semantically, also of the truth value of its *interpretations or readings*, that is, of singular, specific statements, derived from the ambiguous one (although not in a logical way, by deductive inference, but by an empirical analysis of the possibilities of specification), which resolve the ambiguity for those who receive the relevant information conveyed by these sentences.

And after this act we find, now by logical deduction, the truth or falsehood of the indeterminate proposition from which the derivation that adds information begins. Thus, (2) can be interpreted by the person who receives said communication, completing it with other propositions that are obtained by induction or speculation, but that are not included in the ambiguous proposition, whether, for example, as

(2.1) Not every man is just, and men exist;

or as

(2.2) Not every man is just, and men don't exist.

Since Abelard presupposes that no man exists, but neither (1) nor (2) provides such information, upon detecting (of course, another variety of intelligence) that no man exists, she will find that (2.2) is true, while (2.1) it's false.

She will use the exclusive disjunction syntax (*XOR* in Boolean logic) to infer from concrete statements contrary to (1) (and no longer from the contradictory one) that one of them must be true, and therefore the ambiguous statement from which they are derived is also true, by the logical operations of the exclusive XOR ($a = \text{True} \vee b = \text{True} \wedge (a \wedge b = \text{False}) \rightarrow a \text{ XOR } b = \text{True}$, etc.).

Then, a truth value can be assigned to an ambiguous proposition, either because it is

contradictory to another proposition that we know has a different truth value, or because we find that one of its propositions derived, one of its singularities, is true, in which case the abstract proposition is true, or none of its derivations is true, in which case the indeterminate one is false.

According to our analysis, Abelardo's mistake is to think that the contradictory relationship is disabled when the subject is empty, by assigning a truth value *in itself* to an abstract proposition, when, as we have shown, such a statement has a truth value, but it depends entirely on the truth value of the proposition that it negates, and/or on the truth value of its concretization, the derived proposition that is a contrary among more than one, and that is true, excluding the other contraries.

He confuses (2) with (2.2). However, since there is at least another alternative, the contradictory does not match the contrary anymore, and there are two contraries that belong to *E*; that is, we affirm that, while in the Square of Opposition occurs $(2) \in O$, because it is the contradictory of (1), it happens that $(2.2) \in E$, because it is a contrary, as well as $(2.1) \in E$, for being another possible contrary; and in the exclusive disjunction between them, (2.2) must be a true contrary opposite, and its complement (2.1) must be false, and by being so they make (2) true, regardless of how ambiguous it may be. In this way, the Aristotelian definition is satisfied, according to which (1) is false and its contrary is true.

The reasoning of Abelard and others who use (2) to challenge the validity of the classic Square of Logical Opposition is flawed because they overlook the indeterminacy of (2). This does not mean that the Square is necessarily correct or incorrect, but rather that this argument against it is based on false premises, by not considering the relationship between the abstract and the concrete and, with this, the fact that the application of the logical square stops its action when determining, for example, *O* as contradictory to *A*; but determining whether it is an ambiguous or concrete contradictory depends on the universe of discourse, on how many opposing options it provides. If there is only one alternative, then we have a logical *dichotomy*, but if there are more than one, then we have a disjunctive *polytomy*, which requires empirical evidence and not just logical tools [see Kant 17, section 113; and Matus 19, p. 6].

Antithesis to Russell: delimiting the ambiguous and the singular in negation.

A logician who sees the existence of ambiguity in negation, in cases formally similar to what Abelard stated, is Bertrand *Russell*, for example with the approach to propositions

(3) The present king of France is bald; and

(4) The present king of France is not bald.

Because the subject "The present King of France," whether uttered today or in 1905, is empty, the existence predicated is untrue when predicating a property unique to existence (being bald). Russell, on the other hand, thinks that there are two separate criteria for establishing the truth value of the contradictory (4). Since proposition (4) is the contradictory of false (3), it must be true according to the principle of contradiction. However, when searching the world for the present King of France, he is not found. "Perhaps the Hegelians, who love synthesis, will conclude that he

wears a wig," according to his ironic expression. However, he considers that because it is an ambiguous expression, it can be *interpreted* in two ways:

(4.1) There is an entity which is now King of France and is not bald.

(4.2) It is false that there is an entity which is now King of France and is bald.

Thus, it can be directly determined that (4.1) is false because there is no such king; while (4.2) is true for the same reason [21, p. 490].

Russell's analysis is more appropriate than Abelard's, *however* we consider he makes a mistake in his method to determining what the interpretation of the *meaning* of an ambiguous expression is. Such an approach presupposes that (4.1) and (4.2) are the same statement (4) with different meanings, by expressing about (4): "It is false if it means [4.1], but it is true if it means [4.2]" [21, p. 490].

Following his irony, this is equivalent to assuming (4.1) and (4.2) are the same *bald* proposition (4), but with two different wigs; when, in fact, they are two new propositions with their own hair.

(4.1) \neq (4) \neq (4.2).

In the same way as saying

(5) The operating system of that phone is not Linux,

is not the same as saying

(5.1) The operating system of that phone is Windows;

XOR

(5.2) The operating system of that phone is iOS.

With (5) being a more abstract expression, since it does not specify the operating system.

Therefore, the *interpretation or reading*, when singularizing, is an inductive process of the interpreter regarding what specifically the speaker who is interpreted has wanted to say, based, for example, on tying up loose ends. However, this is not a periphrasis, the same thing said in another way, but a proposition different from the indeterminate proposition of origin.

Among various analysts throughout history, as can be seen, e.g., in Horn's exhaustive book [14, p.3], it happens that despite divergences regarding other aspects of negation, there is the idea that exists an asymmetry between affirmation and negation, although there is much speculation about what it may consist of; if, for example, one is primary and the other secondary, or the scope is broad or narrow, etc. And it is even held that negation is always ambiguous, or that it never is.

Contrary to these latter beliefs, we hold that mere negation is *ambiguous* only when there is *more than one opposite* of a proposition. However, when there is a single contrary it is when the

contradictory opposite coincides with the contrary, and therefore here the negation of the contradictory is not ambiguous, since it is enough to stipulate the contradictory to know which is the specific contrary. Thus, there are singular negations that are more informative than abstract negations, and as informative as affirmations.

With this, for example, when the *universe of discourse* is the set of integers, express

(6) The number 57 is not even,

means the same thing as saying

(6.1) The number 57 is odd.

(6.1) is immediately deduced from (6) without any additional premise other than the scope of the universe of discourse; it is not induced or speculated which of more than one possible opposite may be the expressed case.

Precisely, the universe of discourse determines the scope of the topic that the propositions can cover.

Thus, for example, if instead of the integers the set of real numbers is taken as the universe, the expression

(7) The number π is not even,

is not the same that (or does not follow from) saying

(7.1) The number π is odd,

because, given the domain of discourse in which we now find ourselves, there is the option

(7.2) The number π is neither even nor odd.

In this universe of discourse, “not even” is the contradictory of “even”, but it does not mean odd, it is ambiguous, since it can mean that π is a non-integer real number, to which the qualifier even or odd cannot be applied. Here, odd is just one of two or more possible contraries.

Horn says:

One traditional conceit of the asymmetricalist forces is the paradox of negative judgment: if a positive statement refers or corresponds to a positive fact, to what does a negative statement refer or correspond? Clearly not to a negative fact. [14, p.3]

Based on what we have argued, we respond that when there is only *one* possible *opposite* within a universe of discourse, *a negative statement refers at the same time to a specific positive fact*. When there are multiple opposites, the negative statement corresponds to an ambiguity.

Misconception about the so-called category error.

According to *Hart*,

The existence or nonexistence of members of the subject class determines not the truth or falsity of statements of these forms but only the prior question whether the question of their truth or falsity can arise. [12, p.209]

In this sense, *Strawson* affirms that propositions like Russell's (4), with its *empty subject*, have no truth value; but *he does not take into account* the universe of possible discourse of these expressions, as well as that the truth value is given either by the value of a specific proposition of which it is contradictory, or by the value of the propositions derived for its specification. He argues as if there was only one *rigid* universe of discourse and any other was off topic, as it was a *category* mistake.

So, for example, he says:

A literal-minded and childless man asked whether all his children are asleep will certainly not answer 'Yes' on the ground that he has none; but nor will he answer 'No' on this ground. Since he has no children, the question does not arise. [23, p. 344]

However, if the literal-minded person answers "The question does not arise," and does not answer "No; I do not have children," he is considering a universe of discourse that only includes as possible the brief answers {yes, no}; without considering that here the mere "no" is an ambiguous answer that allows to be included in the universe its derivatives

(8.1) Yes I have children and they are not sleeping;

XOR

(8.2) I have no children, and therefore I have no sleeping children.

If the concrete (8.2) is true, then it makes true his abstract "I have no sleeping children."

Bergman points out that

A sortally incorrect statement (non-significant statement, category mistake), in its simplest form, may be characterized as a statement in which the subject and predicate are mismatched. [4, p. 61]

Horn gives as an example

(9.1) Two is red

(9.2) Two is not red,

But we say that this occurs only if we limit the universe of discourse, for example, to the set of real numbers. But if we take such a universe to be the set of any possible properties, then there is no category mistake, and so (9.1) is false. And (9.2) is true.

If we take the example of *Carnap*

(9.3) This stone is now thinking about Vienna.

(9.4) This stone is not now thinking about Vienna,

also admitting as a universe of discourse the class of any possible property, concrete or abstract, and not only the class of the properties of minerals, there is no longer an incorrectly classified sentence. (9.3) is false and (9.4) is true. The *correctness of the classification* in a categorical proposition depends on the universe of discourse that is chosen as a reference.

Critique of proposals that exhibit challenging cases of ambiguity and specificity, highlighting empty subjects and alleged categorization errors.

Addressing a classic example, according to *Frege*, with an expression like

(10.1) Kepler died in misery

There is a presupposition that the name 'Kepler' designates something; but it does not follow that the sense of the sentence 'Kepler died in misery' contains the thought that the name 'Kepler' designates something. If this were the case the negation would have to run not

(10.2) Kepler did not die in misery

but

(10.3) Kepler did not die in misery, or the name 'Kepler' has no reference. [9, p. 34]

Again, there the mere abstract, *contradictory* negation of A is confused with its concrete derivatives *contraries* to A: syntactically the mere negation is (10.2), and in reality it gives rise to two other distinct, singular, concrete propositions, through the connective XOR; that is, à la Abelard, we can assume that Kepler did not exist, that the universe of discourse includes the option that the subject does not refer. And therefore (10.1) is false. While the contradictory of it, (10.2), would be abstract (something that Abelard's or Frege's perspective does not consider) and would derive from it the possible concrete expressions

(10.2a) Kepler existed and did not die in misery,

XOR

(10.2b) Kepler did not exist and did not die in misery.

With (10.2a) false and (10.2b) true. Whether or not Kepler existed, *whether "Kepler" is empty or not*, (10.2) is an indeterminate option, while its derivatives are singular assertions, all with some truth value. Although without the need to reformulate them as *descriptions* in primary or secondary occurrences, in the manner of *Russell*. Thus we avoid, for example, what Henry points out about Russell's analysis:

In the face of such difficulties the distinction which has evidently been desirable all along is introduced in a tortuous and *ad hoc* fashion under the misleading guise of the 'primary and secondary occurrence' of descriptions and all names have to be construed as disguised descriptions in order to be able to take advantage of this *ad hoc* distinction. [13, p. 74]

It is enough to only take into account the singular or ambiguous meaning of the sentences (*regardless of whether they are empty, or they are supposed category errors*) and, with the indeterminate character, the truth or not of any of the exclusive disjunctions derived as contraries, through the interpretation or reading of the contradictory ambiguous expression [for greater detail on this, see Matus 19]. This *avoids* Russell's *ad hoc*, and that empty names "have to be constructed as disguised descriptions," or what *Quine* does to the extreme with the following position:

Now, what of 'Pegasus'? This being a word rather than a descriptive phrase, Russell's argument does not immediately apply to it. However, it can easily be made to apply. We have only to rephrase 'Pegasus' as a description ... 'the thing that is-Pegasus, the thing that 'pegasizes'. [20, p. 27]

And what Horn observes is avoided: "In the present case, we are no longer capable of treating even the most obvious instances of subject-predicate sentences as such." [14, p. 108].

This tendency to not clearly distinguish between the abstract proposition and its concrete derivations —the strict negation being the contradictory and the disambiguations of these being the contraries—; and that the truth value of the former is determined by the fact that, in the exclusive disjunction of the latter, either one is true or all are false, is also found among linguists, e.g., *Chomsky*, who analyzes the utterance

(11.1) John [(doesn't like) mushrooms].

He says:

if John has never tasted mushrooms and it is asserted that he likes them, I can deny the assertion by stating (11.1) interpreting the negation as associated with the predicate phrase, but not by stating John dislikes mushrooms, or (11.1) with the negation interpreted as associated with the verb. [6, p. 191]

But we must consider that (11.1) is indeterminate. "He *doesn't like* them", if used as the mere contradictory, *does not mean* exactly the same as "He *dislikes* them" due to a random drift typical of spoken language (although at the beginning, etymologically, it could have done so). With this, the proposition

(11) John likes mushrooms,

has as its only and mere contradictory to (11.1), the ambiguous. And (11.1) has as possible singular derivations:

(11.2) Juan doesn't like mushrooms, and he already tried them,

XOR

(11.3) Juan doesn't like mushrooms, he hasn't tried them.

The assertion (11) is always denied by (11.1) as its contradictory, regardless of the derived contraries. With the contraries something more than mere negation is stipulated. Thus, (11.1) *plus* "the negation interpreted as associated with the verb" equals (11.3), singular, and is not the same as the mere (11.1), which is indeterminate.

Refuting fallacies about double negation.

By the way, although *Jespersen* notes the aforementioned random drift of language, he arrives at the misleading observation that

For contradictory terms language generally employs either derivatives like *unhappy, impossible, disorder* or composite expressions containing the adverb *not ...* Here the general rule in all (or most) languages is that *not* means 'less than,' or in other words 'between the term qualified and nothing.' Thus *not good* means 'inferior,' but does not comprise 'excellent'; *not lukewarm* indicates a lower temperature than *lukewarm*, something between lukewarm and icy, not something between lukewarm and hot ... Whenever two negatives really refer to the same idea or word (as special negatives) the result is invariably positive; this is true of all languages ... The two negatives, however, do not exactly cancel one another in such a way that the result is identical with the simple *common, frequent, with some doubt*; the longer expression is always weaker: 'this is not unknown to me' or 'I am not ignorant of this' means 'I am to some extent aware of it,' etc. [15, pp. 322, 325 y 332]

And this contributes to what *Horn* mentions,

Double negations don't quite cancel out ... When *not un-X* fails to reduce to *X*, as in (12),

- (12) a. A not unhappy person entered the room.
b. He's a not unhappy person.

What affirmative does this construction equate to? [14, p. 297]

Which appear to be supported by what *Lyons* says:

It seems to be the case that the application of propositional negation to a gradable expression (e.g., 'like') will always tend to produce a contrary, rather than a contradictory, whether the language-system lexicalizes the contrary (e.g., 'dislike ') or not. [18, vol. 2, p. 773]

However, it must be said that if "not" (or "no") comes to mean a contrary "less than", then a contrary not_2 is emerging, *homonym* of the contradictory "not" (not_1). Thus, the language, unless there is some strange example of language that cannot express logical contradictions, will express them either with a "not" (not_1), homonym of the other (the not_2 = "less than"), or with some other name *synonymous* with not_1 , with the difference in meaning depending on the context in which an expression is made.

Let's keep in mind that, since the logical rule of double negation (which results in the initial affirmation) only applies to contradictories, not to contraries, then "not not happy" does cancel out "not happy" (i.e., " $not_1 not_1$ happy" does cancel " not_1 happy").

And if in any language the equivalent of "not unhappy" does not strictly cancel to "happy" (or "not unknown" to "known," or "not good" to "good," or "not lukewarm" to "lukewarm"), then this means that " not_2 happy" or "unhappy" (or " not_2 known", or "unknown", or " not_2 good", or " not_2 lukewarm") have come to mean, due to stochastic *linguistic drift*, something different to " not_1 happy" (or to " not_1 known" or to " not_1 good", or to " not_1 lukewarm") in such a context.

Those are already the expressions₂: " not_1 happy" or " not_1 known" or " not_1 good", or " not_1 warm" *plus* something additional, that is, linguistically they have ceased to be the respective contradictory ones, and have become each one a contrary between at least two. They are no longer the mere negation (the not_1) of "happy" or "known." With this, (12)a and b cannot be an example of linguistic or logical contradictory double negation. The same strict statement is not being contradictorily denied twice.

Something similar happens with *Lyons*, because "dislike" in his example is actually *more than the simple negation* itself, since it is synonymous with one of the two or more possible singular contraries.

As the Stoics already established, there is only one kind of mere, strict, contradictory negation, which denies the entire proposition: "No: such and such." And we have added in this text that it can be the same as the contrary solely if there is only one possible contrary. However, if there is more than one, the contrary whose truth is the case is not obtained until it is specified as a new proposition, which excludes the other concrete propositional possibilities in the disjunction.

Avoiding mistakes in terms of negation, information and ambiguity.

Horn points out,

The marked member of the positive / negative asymmetry, negation, has been recognized by commentators from Plato to Givón as contributing less information to the discourse than the corresponding unmarked affirmative (*My hat is not red vs. My hat is red*). [12, p.157]

However, there is an imprecision in this, because there is only less *information* (from what we have already seen) when there is more than one contrary of what is denied, and therefore there is an ambiguity. But if the contradictory relationship corresponds to a single opposite derivative, the contradictory is not indeterminate, the information is sufficient to obtain a concrete proposition (thus: "Plato is not sick" in the universe of discourse on the health of a living being, which conveys the same information as saying "Plato is healthy").

With this, an error that comes at least as far back as Parmenides and the Megarians is settled. Wheeler points out,

Mourelatos, in *The Route of Parmenides*, presents an interpretation of the logic of the Parmenidean argument ... (1) There can only be, determinate, definite, entities. Being, how things are, is not vague or fuzzy. (2) Negative sentences are indeterminate and indefinite and so can't state how things are ... 'Negative properties' are no more real, if properties are parts of the being of things, than negative persons. ('Who came in?' 'Well, it was not John'. Just as not-John isn't an individual, so not-red isn't a property). Negative expressions, then, necessarily lack reference. [25, pp. 288-289]

Error corrected, since in such examples only expressions are chosen —without they realizing it— to which more than one contrary corresponds, but if we take examples such as the one mentioned about even and odd numbers (or that of {finite, infinite}, etc.), in the adequate universe of discourse, as we have seen, negation is necessarily determined, since in it non-even is a property as concrete, as defined and determined, as even.

Fallacies about opposites, logical connectives, and ambiguous meaning.

If a proposition is uttered that includes logical connectives, the most concrete contraries can be obtained by negating the different terms. Thus, for example, *Sextus Empiricus* says, with respect to propositions

(13) It is day and it is light

and

It is day and it is not light:

According to them [the Stoics] these are not contradictories. Therefore, propositions do not become contradictory merely through the one exceeding the other by a negative. Yes, they say, but they are contradictories if the following condition is also satisfied: the negative is *prefixed* to the proposition in question. [22, p. 95]

Therefore, the negation of (13) is

(13.1) No: it is day and it is light.

and not

It is day and it is not light.

We *add* that the mere contradictory (13.1) is ambiguous, since *from* it can be interpreted, with the properties of the disjunction, three singular propositions, different from it and from each other, which are contrary to (13):

It is not day and it is light;

XOR

It is day and it is no light;

XOR

It is not day and it is no light.

Which of them in this exclusive disjunction is true, or if none of them is true, is something that can only be determined empirically, as there is not a mere *dichotomy* between the affirmation and a single contrary (equal, therefore, to the contradictory), because it is different from the *polytomous* case, when the contradictory is not identical to any of several contraries. After these issues are determined by experience, the truth or falsity of the most ambiguous proposition from which they derive or to which they logically entail is established, syntactically, by the properties of the XOR connective.

This makes *Boethius's* opinion erroneous, who rejects the *Stoic* practice of putting negation before a categorical proposition, since according to him it only invites ambiguity about which term is denied. But Stoic practice is correct, as long as the ambiguity of the resulting proposition is recognized (except when there is only one contrary), and therefore what its singular derivations are.

Grice states that

To say that A or B (interpreted weakly) would be to make a weaker and so less informative statement than to say that A or to say that B ... A less informative statement than would be appropriate in the circumstances.

In this regard, *Horn* mentions the following example:

I cannot felicitously utter (14),
 (14) My wife is either in Oxford or in London
 on this strong reading, if I know for a fact that my wife is in Oxford (and if I
 presume that this fact is relevant to you when I utter (14)). [14, p. 395]

Nevertheless, we must consider that if I am not sure, for example, whether she has already left one place and arrived at the other, or if I do not presume that it is relevant to you, then I can happily emit (14). Since she cannot be in two places at the same time, this disjunction cannot be inclusive. Therefore, it is exclusive. Due to the logical properties of this last connective, at least one of the options, and only one, must be true for (14) to be true. Thus, for (14) to be false, both options must be false. Therefore, the negation of (14) is

(14.1) My wife is neither in Oxford nor in London.

The utterance (14) is ambiguous. The singularities derived from it, and different from it, are:

(14a) My wife is in Oxford.

(14b) My wife is in London.

If one of them is true, it also makes (14) true.

In a similar sense, (14.1) is also abstract. Its derived concretions, and different from it, are many:

(14x) My wife is in ... (anywhere x other place than Oxford or London).

If one of them is true, it also makes (14.1) true.

Similarly, attempting to refute the ambiguity thesis, *Gazdar* argues that it makes a false prediction of the disjunction case, and proposes the assertion

(15) John isn't either patriotic or quixotic.

He states:

If we assume the A [i.e. Ambiguity] theory, then there are two possible semantic representations for (15). These are shown in (15.1) and (15.2) (where p = John is patriotic and q = John is quixotic).

(15.1) $\neg(p \vee q)$

(15.2) $\neg(p \text{ XOR } q)$...

Now (15.1) is equivalent to (15.3), and (15.2) is equivalent to (15.4).

(15.3) $(\neg p) \wedge (\neg q)$,

(15.4) $((\neg p) \wedge (\neg q)) \vee (p \wedge q)$

But (15.4), and hence (15.2), is true when $p \wedge q$ is true. Thus the A theory predicts that there is a reading of (15) whose truth is ensured by (15.5).
 (15.5) John is both patriotic and quixotic.
 But (15) has no such reading and the A theory is thereby falsified.

What Gazdar *fails* to argue is the heart of the matter: why claim that (15) does not have such a reading with its derivative (15.5)? We maintain that it does have such a reading.

First a detail, in (15) there is double ambiguity, due to the copula, and due to the connective of the disjunction, which can be inclusive or exclusive. In the case of the copula, there are 2 possible derivatives

(15a) John exists and is neither patriotic nor quixotic.

(15.b) John does not exist and is neither patriotic nor quixotic.

(15.b) is true or false regardless of whether the disjunction is inclusive or exclusive. And if it is true it makes (15) true and (15a) false.

(15a) is still ambiguous, because it does not specify the type of disjunction. Its derivatives are those that Gazdar establishes formally with (15.1) and (15.2). (15.1) tells us that John exists and is not either *just* patriotic or *just* quixotic; nor both. (15.2) that John exists and is not either *just* patriotic or *just* quixotic; he is both. So, Gazdar does not notice that the interpretation (15.5), being from (15.2), is more accurately

(15.5_{15.2}) John exists and is both patriotic and quixotic, and not *just* patriotic or *just* quixotic,

with which the relationship of (15) with (15.4) and with (15.5) is more obviously noted.

So, we have that (15) is not true or false by itself; it is indeterminate, because its truth value also depends on *whether one* of the less ambiguous options (15.1) or (15.2) is true, in which case it will be true, or neither (15.1) nor (15.2) are true, and in such case (15) will be false.

(15.1) and (15.2) are less ambiguous than (15), but their respective truth depends on another additional and final singularization of both —that is, *it must be taken into account that there are degrees of abstraction or concretion*— in order to make a verification directly with the facts, which are common for (15.1, 15.2), since both refer exclusively to patriotism and quixotism:

(15.1, 15.2)a John is patriotic.

(15.1, 15.2)b John is quixotic.

If both are true, they make (15.1) true, and (15.2) false. And with that, true (15).

If both are false, they make both (15.1) and (15.2) false. And with this, false (15).

If one of these two is true and the other false, it makes (15.2) true and (15.1) false. And by being true (15.2), the latter makes true the ambiguous one of origin, (15).

Thus, Gazdar's argument does not contravene the thesis of semantic ambiguity. And we must realize that (15.1) and (15.2) are not only readings or specifications of (15), but completely different from it; and mutually different given that they contradict each other, when specifying the type of disjunction to which they refer, the inclusive or the non-inclusive, i.e., or both XOR not both.

A fallacy arises when authors inadvertently change the universe of discourse.

There are authors who deny that "the negation of a scalar term really yields either a contradictory or contrary proposition." For example, regarding

(16.1) War and Peace is a good book; and

(16.2) War and Peace is not a good book,

Horn summarizes: "Jespersen's position results in the claim that (16.1) and (16.2) may both be judged false if Tolstoy's masterpiece is excellent." [14, p. 204].

But *Jespersen* does not observe that, if in the universe of discourse that is being taken into account the *scale* includes the set of 3 elements {Excellent, Good, Bad}, then by simply denying (16.1) its resulting contradictory, (16.2), is ambiguous, because it can be specified by its exclusives: excellent XOR bad.

Here again the meaning of the ambiguous expression is confused with its concrete derivatives, as if they were the same expression. If the universe of discourse were by convention only the Manichean set of two elements {Good, Bad}, there would be a single contrary for (16.2), bad, and therefore it would be equal to the contradictory, and then (16.2) would be at the same time the contradictory and contrary proposition of (16.1).

In any case, (16.1) and (16.2) cannot be false at the same time, and therefore they are contradictory, in a 2-option universe. And they are false at the same time only in a universe of more than 2 options, in which, therefore, they are contrary. The illusion in the argument exists because the universe of discourse is inadvertently changed from a dichotomous scale to a different, polytomous one, by confusing the expressions. And the same thing happens with the relationship some – all, or possible - necessary, thus being false what Horn mentions,

In each case, one member of the pair -the weaker element (*good, some, possible*)- appears to be simultaneously compatible and incompatible with its stronger counterpart (*excellent, all, necessary*). [14, p. 208]

This is not something that happens *simultaneously*.

Similar is the case raised by *Wales and Grieve*, taking up Jespersen's example, according to which if we have

(17.1) The drink is hot,

and its denial

(17.2) The drink is not hot,

The first hint of trouble in regarding negation as an operation on statements becomes apparent when we try to operate in the opposite direction, for we do not know in any precise way the meaning of (17.2) since it is variable. In fact it is infinitely variable—here we will artificially restrict consideration to two points along the hot-cold continuum, which we will label "lukewarm" and "cold." That is, then, we cannot distinguish between (17.2a) and (17.2b) as senses of (17.2):

(17.2a) The drink is cold

(17.2b) The drink is lukewarm

So far so bad, for we can see that it is unwarranted to argue that negating (17.2) lies in an operation that simply deletes *not* from (17.2) to produce (17.1) ... Negation as an operation on statements does not always deal satisfactorily with negative statements ... unless we know the specific sense of the negative statement. [24, pp.327-328]

But they do not realize that the *meaning* of (17.2), being ambiguous, *remains ambiguous, it is not variable*. Those that are variables are, in this case, the possibilities of emissions contrary to (17.1), those that expand (17.2) but are not equal to it. They handle, like Russell, the ambiguous contradiction (17.2) as if it were the *same expression* (although more clearly stated, i.e. its meaning), as that of the contraries (17.2a) or (17.2b); and for this reason they believe that arguing about the latter is the same as arguing about (17.2). But the negation of (17.2a) or (17.2b) is in no way the same as the negation of (17.2).

And so, for example, (17.2a) has as contradictory

(17.2a.1) The drink is not cold;

which is not specific and can be made singular with another different proposition, such as (17.1) or (17.2b), when the universe of discourse used is the set {Hot XOR Lukewarm XOR Cold}, and not just {Hot XOR Cold}. If the universe of discourse adheres to the latter, also restricting consideration, now to just one point on the continuum (that depends on the information we can or want to give or receive), then (17.2) is the only contrary of (17.1), and it is univocal.

Similarly, there is *Strawson's* example:

(18.1) He cares

(18.2) He doesn't care.

(18.2) is the ambiguous contradictory of (18.1), since it has concrete options, which are contrary to (18.1):

(18.2a) He doesn't care because he's dead,

XOR

(18.2b) He doesn't care because he is indolent,

XOR

(18.2x) He doesn't care because x.

With what has been said, we then have that it is false *Lyons'* assertion that

It seems to be the case that the application of propositional negation to a gradable expression (e.g., 'like') will always tend to produce a contrary, rather than a contradictory, whether the language-system lexicalizes the contrary (e.g., 'dislike ') or not. [18, p. 773]

Depending on the universe of discourse, as an essential part of the linguistic context of the proposition in which we are locating ourselves, the "no" in natural language will be either contradictory or contrary. If it is contradictory, it gives us only two logical options, either the affirmation or its strict denial; If it is contrary (and if there is more than one possible contrary) it places us in a universe of discourse with three or more options.

According to *Jespersen*,

We therefore may set up a tripartition :

- A. Positive.
- B. Questionable.
- C. Negative.

A and C are absolute and imply certainty, B implies uncertainty, and in that respect B is the negative counterpart of the two positive sentences A "it is certain that he is rich " and C "it is certain that he is not rich." ... Thus also the adverbs:

- A. always, everywhere
- B. sometimes, somewhere
- O. never, nowhere. ...

[Also] the tripartition between:

- A. Necessity,
- B. Possibility,
- C. Impossibility ...

[And also]

- A. Command,
- B. Permission,
- C. Prohibition. [15, pp. 322 – 325]

But you need to consider that not only uncertainty causes the negative counterpart, and that also, in all those situations that he cites, not only B is the negative counterpart of the two modalities or

phrases A and C (that is, it has A and C as possible contraries, while its mere contradictory negation, not B, is ambiguous and from it A, C are derivations), but, likewise, A is the negative counterpart of the two sentences B and C (with its ambiguous contradictory one, not A, and the derivatives, contraries, B, C); and C is the negative counterpart of the two sentences B and C. Likewise, it does not take into account that discourse universes of only two options are logically possible, for example, respectively, positive and negative in a computer language; a Cosmos where any event always or never occurs, or where there is only need or impossibility; a political regime where only mandates and prohibitions exist.

Proposal of a restriction to the Aristotelian definition of the logical contrary.

We also have the opposition

(19.1) y is odd

(19.2) y is even.

Horn says:

For Aristotle, the sentences in (19.1), (19.2) are also in contrary opposition, although their middle is excluded. If y denotes an integer either (19.1) or (19.2) will indeed be true and the other false. But if y happens to be Socrates, both (19.1) y (19.2) are false. [14, pp. 268-269]

Let's analyze: as we already saw, by taking the universe of discourse of y as the set of integers, then there is only one contrary of "odd", and therefore that contrary, "even", is equal to the contradictory, and hence they cannot be true or false at the same time. But other universes of discourse may exist.

Thus, if we say that y is Socrates, we have changed, *expanding it*, the universe of discourse, for example, to the set of all things. There is already more than one contrary here, and none of them, which are concrete, coincides with the contradictory one, which has become abstract due to this expansion, whose scope is *not simultaneous* with that of the other, abandoned universe. And therefore "odd" has ceased to be equal to the mere contradictory of "even", both have become false predicates at the same time because both have become contraries with more than one opposition in another universe of discourse.

That is, it is appropriate to *restrict the definition of contraries* made from Aristotle (those that cannot be true together, but both of them can be false at the same time [see 3, De Interpretatione: 17^b6]), to describe that logical fact with:

Contrary opposites_{def.} *Both cannot be true together, but both of them can be false at the same time if and only if at least to one of them corresponds two or more possible singularizations of meaning within a given universe of discourse.*

If y denotes an integer, (19.1) and (19.2) are *contradictory and contrary at the same time*, and in

this and *all equivalent cases the most restrictive relationship, the contradictory one, imposes the logical limit: they cannot be true or false at the same time.*

If *y* denotes Socrates, they are contraries that are not merely contradictory. Not observing this implies falling into a fallacy of inadvertent change of the universe of discourse.

Conclusions.

In this paper we wanted to highlight the following basic points:

1. The negation of an expression is *univocal* only when there is a single contrary of what is negated; that is, when this is identified with the contradictory. When there are two or more contraries, the negation is *ambiguous*.
2. When an utterance has an ambiguous meaning, *singular propositions* about concrete possible situations that eliminate ambiguity can be derived from it, not syntactically, but based on experience. Such singulars are propositions with a different meaning from the ambiguous one they singularize. *The ambiguous contradictory negation of an X expression remains ambiguous even if it is clarified, since the clarifications correspond to other different propositions, with more specific information, contraries to the initial proposition X.*
3. An ambiguous proposition does have a *truth value*, but it *depends*, on the one hand, on the truth value, if we know it, of the proposition it negates, by the principle of contradiction; as well as, on the other hand, of the truth value of its singularizations, by the operation of exclusive disjunction.
4. There may be *degrees of ambiguity* of a proposition; its truth value depends on finding the truth value of its *ultimate singularities*, always different from it.
5. When a term is *empty*, the proposition in which it appears does not cease to have a truth value. Having it depends on the relationship between the ambiguous and the singular. Therefore, objections such as Abelardo's regarding the classical *Logical Square of Opposition* are not applicable.
6. There is also *no category error*, as conceived by Frege, Strawson and others; that belief derives from a fallacious and inadvertent change in the universe of discourse.
7. The appropriate distinction between the ambiguous and the specific *avoids ad hoc* formulations, such as that of Russell in his *Theory of Descriptions*. It is enough to resort to the consideration of the principle of contradiction, the degree of ambiguity of the propositions, and the exclusive disjunction.
8. Contrary to what is maintained by various authors, the negation of *scalar terms* can always yield clearly stipulated contradictory and contrary propositions. Their position occurs because they confuse ambiguous expressions with their concrete derivations, and from this they carry out a fallacy of inadvertent *change of the universe of discourse*. And that is why they think that it occurs at the same time that propositions are contrary and contradictory in cases when there are more

than two options of contrary opposites.

9. From all this, a *modification* emerges to the Aristotelian *definition* of contraries (as those that cannot be true together; but both of them can be false at the same time), that is:

Contrary opposites are those that cannot be true together; but both of them can be false at the same time *if and only if* to any of them corresponds two or more possible singularizations of meaning within a given universe of discourse.

If, otherwise, there is only one possible singularity, the contradictory is equal to the only contrary, and the *greatest restriction, the contradictory relationship, imposes the logical limit*: they cannot be true or false at the same time.

Finally, we can consider that the elements stipulated in this paper can be used as an Ariadne's thread that constitutes an adequate guide to get out of the labyrinth of several of the problems raised around logical negation.

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